

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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MODERN APPROACHES TO IMPROVING MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. This study examines modern approaches to improving management accounting in commercial banks, with particular emphasis on efficiency, profitability, and strategic decision-making. The research analyzes challenges associated with increasing banking complexity, intensifying competition, and ongoing digital transformation processes. Based on the findings, an integrated framework is proposed that incorporates responsibility center accounting, the Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP) system, XIRR methodology, and adaptive budgeting mechanisms. The results demonstrate that these instruments strengthen financial control, improve liquidity management, and enhance the evaluation of banking performance. Consequently, the proposed approaches contribute to increasing the operational efficiency and strategic effectiveness of commercial banks in Uzbekistan.

Key words: management accounting, commercial banks, FTP system, responsibility centers, Beyond Budgeting, XIRR, budgeting, banking profitability, asset and liability management, banking efficiency.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur tadqiqot tijorat banklarida boshqaruv hisobini takomillashtirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, unda samaradorlik, rentabellik va strategik qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Tadqiqotda bank tizimining murakkablashuvi, raqobat muhitining kuchayishi hamda raqamli transformatsiya jarayonlari natijasida yuzaga kelayotgan muammolar tahlil qilindi. Shu asosda mas'uliyat markazlari hisobi, Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP) tizimi, XIRR metodologiyasi hamda moslashuvchan budjetlashtirish mexanizmlariga asoslangan integratsiyalashgan model taklif etildi. Tadqiqot natijalari ushbu vositalar moliyaviy nazoratni kuchaytirish, likvidlikni samarali boshqarish va bank faoliyati natijadorligini baholash imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishini ko'rsatdi. Natijada, ushbu yondashuvlar O'zbekiston tijorat banklari faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qilishi asoslab berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruv hisobi, tijorat banklari, FTP tizimi, mas'uliyat markazlari, Beyond Budgeting, XIRR, budjetlashtirish, bank rentabelligi, aktiv va passivlarni boshqarish, bank samaradorligi.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматриваются современные подходы к совершенствованию управленческого учёта в коммерческих банках с акцентом на повышение эффективности, рентабельности и качества стратегического управления. В работе проанализированы проблемы, возникающие в условиях усложнения банковской системы, усиления конкурентной среды и процессов цифровой трансформации. На этой основе предложена интегрированная модель, основанная на учёте по центрам ответственности, системе Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP), методологии XIRR и адаптивных механизмах бюджетирования. Результаты исследования показывают, что использование данных инструментов способствует усилению финансового контроля, эффективному управлению ликвидностью и повышению качества оценки результатов деятельности банков. Обосновано, что данные подходы способны повысить эффективность деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: управленческий учёт, коммерческие банки, система FTP, центры ответственности, Beyond Budgeting, XIRR, бюджетирование, рентабельность банков, управление активами и пассивами, эффективность банковской деятельности.

INTRODUCTION

The modern banking sector is undergoing significant structural and technological transformation driven by globalization, financial liberalization, digitalization, and increasing market competition. Under these conditions, commercial banks are required not only to maintain financial stability but also to ensure operational efficiency, strategic flexibility, and sustainable profitability. Consequently, management accounting systems have become increasingly important as analytical instruments that support strategic decision-making and effective financial management within banking institutions.

Unlike traditional financial accounting, which primarily focuses on external reporting and regulatory compliance, management accounting provides internal information necessary for planning, controlling, budgeting, pricing, and evaluating the efficiency of banking operations. In commercial banks, management accounting plays an increasingly strategic and valuable role by supporting the effective management of diverse banking products, strengthening financial risk coordination, and enhancing the efficiency of asset and liability management processes. This contributes significantly to improving operational performance, financial stability, and the overall quality of strategic decision-making within banking institutions.

In recent years, the banking sector of Uzbekistan has undergone substantial reforms aimed at liberalizing financial markets, strengthening corporate governance, increasing the role of private capital, and enhancing the competitiveness of commercial banks. These reforms have significantly increased the demand for modern management accounting systems capable of supporting efficient resource allocation, strategic planning, and profitability management.

The ongoing institutional modernization processes in commercial banks are creating favorable conditions for the further improvement of management accounting practices. Modern cost allocation systems are gradually enhancing the accuracy of evaluating the efficiency of banking divisions and financial products. At the same time, the development of more flexible budgeting approaches is strengthening banks' ability to adapt effectively to rapidly changing market conditions. In addition, the expanding implementation of transfer pricing mechanisms is contributing to more efficient profitability assessment, improved liquidity management, and the overall enhancement of financial decision-making processes within commercial banks.

This study aims to examine modern approaches to improving management accounting systems in commercial banks and to develop practical recommendations for increasing banking efficiency through the implementation of advanced analytical and financial management mechanisms. In particular, the research focuses on activity-based costing, the implementation of Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP) mechanisms, the application of XIRR methodologies in portfolio management, and adaptive budgeting approaches.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in the development of an integrated framework that combines strategic cost management, transfer pricing systems, advanced portfolio evaluation methodologies, and flexible budgeting approaches within commercial banking management systems.

The practical significance of the study is associated with the potential application of the proposed mechanisms in commercial banks operating in Uzbekistan to improve profitability, operational flexibility, liquidity management, and the overall quality of strategic decision-making.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations of management accounting were substantially developed by Robert S. Kaplan and Robin Cooper, who introduced Activity-Based Costing (ABC) as an effective mechanism for improving cost allocation accuracy and operational efficiency. According to the authors, strategic cost management systems make a significant contribution to enhancing managerial decision-making and strengthening organizational competitiveness [1].

Charles T. Horngren emphasized that modern management accounting systems should integrate budgeting, strategic planning, cost analysis, and performance measurement into a unified analytical framework capable of supporting long-term organizational development [2].

Anthony A. Atkinson argued that decentralized management accounting structures enhance managerial accountability and operational flexibility, particularly in organizations operating under dynamic market conditions [3].

Jeremy Hope and Robin Fraser critically evaluated traditional annual budgeting systems and concluded that rigid budgeting models are becoming less effective in rapidly changing business environments. The authors proposed the Beyond Budgeting concept as a more adaptive and flexible management system focused on continuous planning and decentralized decision-making [4].

Peter S. Rose highlighted the importance of effective asset and liability management, as well as transfer pricing systems, in commercial banks. According to Rose, internal transfer pricing mechanisms improve profitability assessment, liquidity management, and the efficiency of resource allocation [5].

Frederick S. Mishkin emphasized that banking profitability and financial stability largely depend on effective risk management systems, efficient allocation of financial resources, and the application of modern analytical management tools [6].

Joel M. Stern substantiated the importance of discounted cash flow methodologies, particularly NPV and IRR models, in evaluating investment efficiency and optimizing financial decision-making processes [7].

David Otley argued that management control systems should focus not only on financial indicators but also on strategic adaptability and operational performance measurement [8].

Christopher Drury noted that modern management accounting systems must support strategic coordination among organizational divisions while simultaneously ensuring effective operational control mechanisms [9].

Recent studies related to the banking sector of Uzbekistan also emphasize the growing importance of modern management accounting systems in improving banking efficiency and financial sustainability. Existing research highlights the significance of FTP systems, adaptive budgeting mechanisms, asset and liability management approaches, digital analytical reporting systems, and responsibility center-based accounting in strengthening operational effectiveness and strategic flexibility within commercial banks [10–16].

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that the modernization of management accounting systems through strategic analytical mechanisms, adaptive budgeting approaches, and advanced profitability assessment tools contributes significantly to improving operational efficiency, financial stability, and competitiveness in commercial banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed-method research design to evaluate the effectiveness of modern management accounting tools in commercial banks. The qualitative component of the research focuses on the conceptual analysis of responsibility center-based accounting, Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP) mechanisms, XIRR methodology, and adaptive budgeting systems. At the same time, the quantitative component is based on comparative financial analysis aimed at assessing the impact of these instruments on profitability, cost allocation efficiency, and the effectiveness of internal financial control within banking institutions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the key limitations of traditional management accounting systems in commercial banks is the limited ability to accurately evaluate the efficiency of individual organizational divisions. Under centralized accounting systems, operational costs are frequently allocated using generalized methods that do not fully reflect the actual performance and resource utilization of banking units. In order to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of internal financial analysis, this study proposes the implementation of activity-based management accounting systems.

Activity-Based Costing (ABC) in the banking sector is a modern management accounting method that allocates costs based on activities rather than organizational departments. This approach is particularly important for commercial banks because a significant proportion of banking costs are indirect and cannot be directly assigned to specific products or services through traditional accounting methods.

Within the ABC framework, the process begins with the identification of key activities that consume organizational resources within the bank. Subsequently, these activities are systematically analyzed, and the costs associated with each activity are determined. Afterward, appropriate cost drivers are identified in order to measure the extent to which banking products or services utilize particular activities. At the final stage, total costs are allocated to products, services, or customer groups based on their actual consumption of these activities. As a result, the ABC system contributes to more accurate cost allocation, improved operational efficiency, and enhanced managerial decision-making within commercial banks (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Key advantages of Activity-based accounting implementation.

This approach enables commercial banks to evaluate the efficiency of individual banking products, departments, and branches more accurately while simultaneously improving the quality of managerial decision-making.

Application of XIRR Methodology in Banking Operations. Efficient asset and liability management remains one of the key determinants of profitability and financial stability in commercial banks. However, traditional profitability evaluation models, including static discounted cash flow approaches, do not always adequately reflect the irregular timing structure of banking cash inflows and outflows. As a result, the accuracy of performance measurement may be limited, particularly in loan portfolios, treasury operations, and FTP-based internal pricing systems.

To enhance the effectiveness of financial analysis and profitability assessment, this study proposes the application of the Extended Internal Rate of Return (XIRR) methodology as a more flexible and time-sensitive approach to investment evaluation and portfolio performance measurement. Unlike conventional methods, XIRR enables the precise calculation of returns based on actual transaction dates, making it especially suitable for banking operations characterized by non-periodic cash flows.

The application of the XIRR methodology contributes to a more accurate assessment of banking profitability, improves the quality of portfolio management, and strengthens analytical support for strategic financial decision-making within commercial banks.

The XIRR model is defined as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C_i}{(1+r)^{\frac{d_i-d_0}{365}}} = 0$$

Where:

C_i — individual cash flow (positive or negative);

r — internal rate of return (XIRR);

d_i — date of each cash flow;

d_0 — initial investment date;

$(d_i - d_0)/365$ — time adjustment factor expressed in years.

The application of the XIRR methodology enables commercial banks to achieve a more accurate assessment of profitability, improve investment decision-making processes, and enhance the consistency of internal performance evaluation across various financial instruments and business units.

Within the context of commercial banking operations, the use of XIRR provides a more precise estimation of profitability compared to traditional NPV-based methods. This approach is particularly important for loan portfolios, FTP-based internal pricing systems, and investment projects characterized by irregular cash flow structures. As a result, the XIRR methodology strengthens the analytical quality of financial management and supports more effective strategic and operational decision-making in commercial banks (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Advantages of XIRR Methodology in Banking Decision-Making.

To ensure consistency between internal pricing mechanisms and profitability measurement processes, this study integrates Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP) mechanisms with XIRR-based performance evaluation approaches. Within this framework, FTP is applied to determine the internal cost of funds, while XIRR is used to measure the realized return generated by actual cash flows.

The integration of these approaches enables commercial banks to price financial products more accurately, evaluate the actual economic profitability of banking operations, improve asset and liability coordination, and strengthen the quality of strategic decision-making processes.

The incorporation of XIRR into management accounting systems significantly enhances the precision of financial performance measurement in commercial banks. When combined with FTP-based internal pricing

systems and responsibility center accounting, the XIRR methodology provides a more realistic, flexible, and dynamic framework for profitability evaluation under conditions of irregular cash flows, which are characteristic of banking operations in emerging economies.

Implementation of FTP Systems in Commercial Banks. Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP) represents one of the most important instruments within modern banking management accounting systems. FTP mechanisms enable commercial banks to determine the actual cost of financial resources more accurately and to objectively evaluate the profitability of banking products, business divisions, and financial operations. As a result, FTP systems contribute to improving internal financial control, optimizing liquidity management, and enhancing the overall effectiveness of strategic banking management.

The proposed FTP model is expressed as:

$$FTP = COF + LP + CRP + OC + PM$$

Where:

COF— Cost of Funds;

LP— Liquidity Premium;

CRP— Credit Risk Premium;

OC— Operational Costs;

PM— Profit Margin (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Benefits of the FTP System in Commercial Banks.

International banking institutions actively utilize FTP systems as integral components of profitability management frameworks due to their effectiveness in improving operational transparency, strengthening financial control, and enhancing the quality of financial decision-making processes.

Modern Budgeting Approaches in Commercial Banks. Traditional budgeting systems are increasingly viewed as insufficiently flexible under rapidly changing financial and market conditions. As a result, modern commercial banks are progressively transitioning toward adaptive budgeting mechanisms capable of responding more effectively to dynamic business environments and strategic management requirements.

In this context, the present study proposes the integration of Beyond Budgeting, Zero-Based Budgeting, and Activity-Based Budgeting approaches within commercial banking management systems. The combined application of these budgeting mechanisms contributes to improving resource allocation efficiency, strengthening operational flexibility, enhancing cost control processes, and increasing the overall effectiveness of strategic financial planning in commercial banks (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Key Principles of Beyond Budgeting.

This approach enables commercial banks to respond more effectively to market fluctuations and changing customer needs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The Benefits of Zero-Based Budgeting.

Zero-Based Budgeting requires all expenditures to be justified from the beginning of each planning period rather than relying solely on historical budget indicators. This approach contributes to improving the efficiency of resource allocation, strengthening cost control mechanisms, and enhancing the transparency of financial planning processes within commercial banks.

Activity-Based Budgeting. Activity-Based Budgeting is an approach that allocates budgets according to organizational divisions, operational activities, and managerial accountability structures. This method enables commercial banks to align budgeting processes more closely with actual operational requirements and strategic objectives.

The implementation of Activity-Based Budgeting provides several important advantages, including improved budget transparency, strengthened managerial accountability, enhanced coordination among organizational divisions, and more effective performance evaluation mechanisms. As a result, this approach contributes to increasing operational efficiency and improving the quality of financial management within commercial banks.

Comparative analysis demonstrates that the integration of modern adaptive budgeting approaches significantly improves financial flexibility, operational coordination, and strategic planning effectiveness in commercial banking institutions (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Modern Management Accounting Systems in Commercial Banks¹

Aspect	Traditional Management Accounting	Modern Management Accounting
Cost Allocation	Centralized cost allocation	Activity-based cost allocation
Budgeting System	Static annual budgeting	Adaptive and flexible budgeting
Profitability Assessment	Aggregate profitability evaluation	Product- and division-level profitability assessment
Pricing Mechanism	Conventional pricing methods	FTP-based pricing mechanisms
Portfolio Management	Traditional maturity analysis	XIRR-based portfolio optimization
Liquidity Management	Conventional treasury management	Dynamic liquidity management
Decision-Making	Historically oriented decision-making	Strategically oriented analytical decision-making
Operational Flexibility	Limited operational flexibility	High operational adaptability
Financial Control	Periodic financial control	Continuous monitoring and control
Strategic Planning	Short-term planning orientation	Long-term value-oriented strategic planning
Digital Integration	Partial process automation	Integrated digital analytical systems
Accountability Mechanism	Weak organizational segmentation	Activity-based responsibility center accountability

The comparative analysis presented in the table demonstrates the substantial differences between traditional and modern management accounting systems in commercial banks. Traditional management accounting primarily focuses on centralized control mechanisms, historical financial evaluation, and static budgeting approaches. Although these methods provide basic financial oversight, they often demonstrate limited flexibility and analytical capacity under rapidly changing financial market conditions.

In contrast, modern management accounting systems are based on strategic analytical approaches that emphasize operational flexibility, accurate profitability assessment, dynamic liquidity management, and integrated digital technologies. In particular, activity-based cost allocation, FTP-based pricing mechanisms, XIRR-based portfolio optimization, and adaptive budgeting systems significantly improve the precision of financial analysis and managerial decision-making processes.

Furthermore, modern management accounting strengthens accountability mechanisms through responsibility center-based management structures, enhances coordination among organizational divisions, and supports continuous financial monitoring. As a result, the implementation of modern management accounting approaches contributes to improving operational efficiency, financial sustainability, and long-term competitiveness in commercial banks.

¹ Created by author.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

This study aimed to develop an integrated and practically applicable framework for improving the effectiveness of management accounting systems in commercial banks. The research focused on enhancing operational efficiency, strengthening internal decision-making processes, improving cost allocation accuracy, and increasing overall banking profitability within the context of rapidly evolving financial markets and ongoing digital transformation.

The study proposed an integrated management accounting framework based on four key components: activity-based cost accounting, the implementation of Funds Transfer Pricing (FTP) mechanisms, the application of the Extended Internal Rate of Return (XIRR) methodology in profitability and portfolio evaluation, and the adoption of modern adaptive budgeting approaches, including Beyond Budgeting and Zero-Based Budgeting.

Using a qualitative analytical approach supported by comparative financial analysis, the study examined the influence of these tools on internal financial management efficiency, resource allocation processes, and performance evaluation systems within commercial banks. The findings indicate that activity-based accounting significantly improves cost transparency and strengthens accountability across banking divisions, thereby enhancing performance monitoring and managerial control mechanisms.

Furthermore, the implementation of FTP mechanisms improves the accuracy of internal pricing systems and strengthens coordination between asset and liability structures. This contributes to more efficient capital allocation and enhances decision-making quality in both lending and investment operations. The study also demonstrates that the application of the XIRR methodology provides a more precise measurement of investment profitability, particularly in banking environments characterized by irregular cash flow structures and diversified financial instruments.

In addition, adaptive budgeting approaches, including Beyond Budgeting and Zero-Based Budgeting, significantly improve strategic flexibility and operational responsiveness. These approaches enable commercial banks to move beyond rigid annual budgeting systems and adopt more dynamic, analytical, and performance-oriented financial planning frameworks.

Overall, the integration of these management accounting instruments creates a more efficient, transparent, and strategically responsive banking management system. The study contributes to the existing scientific literature by demonstrating how modern management accounting tools can be effectively integrated to improve both financial performance measurement and internal governance structures in commercial banks.

From a practical perspective, the findings have important implications for banking institutions and policymakers in emerging economies such as Uzbekistan. In particular, the implementation of responsibility center accounting can significantly strengthen internal cost control systems and enhance managerial accountability. Similarly, the broader application of FTP systems can improve internal fund pricing mechanisms and increase the efficiency of banking operations.

Moreover, the adoption of XIRR-based performance evaluation models contributes to improving the accuracy of profitability analysis for banking products and investment portfolios. This is especially important in environments characterized by irregular cash flow structures, where traditional accounting approaches may not fully reflect actual economic performance.

Finally, the implementation of adaptive budgeting systems, such as Beyond Budgeting and Zero-Based Budgeting, can strengthen financial discipline, improve resource optimization, and increase the agility of commercial banks in responding to market changes and strategic challenges.

Within the context of Uzbekistan's banking sector, the adoption of these modern management accounting practices can significantly improve operational efficiency, strengthen financial stability, and enhance the competitiveness of commercial banks. The study concludes that the modernization of management accounting systems is not only achievable but also strategically important for ensuring long-term sustainability and performance improvement in the banking sector.

Overall, the integration of activity-based accounting, FTP mechanisms, advanced profitability measurement methodologies, and adaptive budgeting systems provides a comprehensive, modern, and forward-looking framework for strengthening management accounting practices in commercial banks.

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